

It seems as if 2011 just flew by, with the DDI Alliance expanding into new directions and becoming increasingly relevant in the research data world. With this expansion the DDI community welcomes new people into its ranks, leading to new collaborations and exciting new projects. Here's to a productive and successful 2012!

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

DwB to Support Access to European Official Microdata

By Mari Kleemola

European official statistical microdata are currently under-used and held behind national, legislative, technical, and cultural borders. The new four-year [Data without Boundaries Project](#) (DwB), funded by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Programme of Research and Development, aims at improving access to these microdata. Among the 20+ project partners are several CESSDA archives, national statistical institutes, and universities. Many project partners are members of the DDI Alliance.

The project consists of 12 complementary and interrelated work packages, of which two deal with metadata standards: WP7 Standards Development and

WP8 Improving Resource Discovery for Official Statistics Data. Both are led by DDI Alliance members, WP7 by the Swedish National Data Service (SND) and WP8 by the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) from the Netherlands. The two work packages will identify the standards that have future relevance for European social science data infrastructure needs and chart the current official statistics metadata and associated interchange formats. The information will be used to create a metadata model that incorporates standards like [SDMX](#) and DDI, as well as any system-specific enrichment required to deliver extended portal functionality. The members of the work packages will also participate in the [SDMX/DDI Dialogue](#).

To advance awareness of metadata issues and cooperation among the

stakeholders, the DwB organized a [workshop on metadata standards](#) last December, following EDDI 2011 in Gothenburg, Sweden. The workshop provided an opportunity to present and discuss the relevant metadata standards and to identify the benefits as well as pitfalls in

These amazing DDI mittens were knitted by Mari Kleemola's mother. Note the 0's and 1's in addition to the DDI logo!

metadata capture and production. In particular, the workshop focused on DDI, SDMX, and the [Generic Statistical Business Process Model \(GSBPM\)](#).

Mari Kleemola is Information Services Manager at the Finnish Data Archive (FSD) and is Vice Chair of the DDI Expert Committee.

Successful Third EDDI Meeting Held in Gothenburg

Hosted by the [Swedish National Data Service](#) (SND), in Gothenburg, Sweden, the third [European DDI Users Group Meeting](#) was held on December 5-6, 2011. By all accounts, it was a very successful meeting with 78 participants from 17 countries and two international organizations in attendance. The [24 EDDI presentations](#) are now available on the Web site.

[GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences](#), and [IDSC of IZA - International Data Service Center of the Institute for the Study of Labor](#) served as co-organizers. Over 50 people took the two DDI courses, which focused on business and technical perspectives.

[Bo Sundgren](#) delivered the Keynote speech on “Communicating in time and space - How to overcome incompatible frames of reference of producers and users of archival data.” His [paper](#) is now part of the [DDI Working Paper Series](#).

Several other meetings occurred in close proximity to EDDI, including a meeting on Qualitative Data, a meeting of the Data Without Boundaries project (see page 1), a Developers meeting, and a

meeting of the group working on an [RDF](#) expression of DDI.

The [Norwegian Social Science Data Service](#) (NSD) has volunteered to host EDDI 2012 at their headquarters in Bergen, Norway, on December 3-4, 2012.

Member Joins the Alliance

The Alliance is pleased to welcome the [Institute for Social and Economic Research](#) (ISER) into the Alliance. Randy Banks will serve as the DDI Alliance Representative from ISER.

Alliance Attends HLG-BAS Workshop in Geneva

Joachim Wackerow from GESIS represented the DDI Alliance at a meeting on [Strategic Developments in Business Architecture in Statistics](#) held October 30-November 1 in Geneva. Achim took part in sessions focusing on the [Generic Statistical Information Model](#) (GSIM), a reference model being developed to define information required to drive statistical production processes and output.

DDI Alliance Working Groups: Status Updates

The [Survey Design and Implementation \(SDI\) group](#) has split into two subgroups to cover (1) Paradata and (2) Weighting/Non-response Adjustment. The Paradata Group is chaired by

Professor Bo Sundgren delivered the Keynote Address at EDDI 2011. Photo credit: Joachim Wackerow

Sue Ellen Hansen, University of Michigan, Survey Research Operations (SRO), with members:

- Kirstine Kolsrud, Norwegian Social Science Data Service
- Anita Rocha, University of Washington, Center for Studies in Demography & Ecology (CSDE)
- Daniel Zahs, University of Michigan, SRO
- Adam Zammit, Australian Consortium for Social and Political Research Incorporated (ACSPRI)

The Weighting and Non-response Adjustment Group is chaired by Peter Granda, University of Michigan, ICPSR, with members:

- Dan Gillman, U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics
- Amanda Norton, Australian Bureau of Statistics
- Bryce Sloane, Australian Bureau of Statistics

Wendy Thomas, University of Minnesota Population Center, serves as the liaison to the Technical Implementation

Committee (TIC) of DDI and is in both SDI subgroups.

The [Governance Task Force](#) is looking at governance issues developing out of the recent DDI external review. The group has split into smaller groups to focus on specific parts of the draft Bylaws.

The DDI [Tools Catalog Group](#) has a new chair – Andias Wira-Alam, from GESIS in Germany.

Dagstuhl Workshops, 2011 and 2012

Two advanced seminars, which will result in Working Papers, were held in September 2011 at Schloss Dagstuhl in Wadern, Germany:

- [Semantic Statistics for Social, Behavioural, and Economic Sciences: Leveraging the DDI Model for the Web](#)

- [Second seminar on “DDI: Managing Metadata for Longitudinal Data – Best Practices”](#)

Another seminar on Semantic Statistics will take place at Dagstuhl on October 15-19, 2012. The topic for the second Dagstuhl seminar in 2012 (October 22-26) is still under discussion.

NCRN Award Made to CISER for DDI Work

Cornell University has received a \$3M NSF Census Research Network award entitled “The Cornell NSF-Census Research Node: Integrated Research Support, Training and Data Documentation.” According to Bill Block, Director of the Cornell Institute for Social and Economic Research (CISER), this project will have a substantial DDI component embodied in the design and implementation of a Comprehensive Census Bureau Metadata Repository (CCBMR).

The CCBMR will be a DDI-based data curation system that will permit synchronization between the public and confidential instances of the repository. The scholarly community will be able to use the CCBMR as it would a conventional metadata repository, deprived only of the values of certain confidential information, but not their metadata. The authorized user, working on the secure Census Bureau network, could use the CCBMR with full information in authorized domains.

Richard Cyganiak diagrams RDF schema at the EDDI meeting in Gothenburg. Photo credit: Joachim Wackerow

2012 Meeting Date Set

The DDI Expert Committee will meet on Monday, June 4, 2012, in Washington, DC, in advance of the [IASSIST 2012](#) meeting to be held June 5-8.

New Version of DDI Codebook Specification Published

After approval in November 2011 by the DDI Expert Committee, [DDI Codebook Version 2.5](#) was officially published on January 17, 2012.

QR Code for DDI Web Site Available

[QR code](#) that stores the URL of the DDI Alliance Web site has been created. A QR (Quick Response) code is a type of barcode that can be scanned and deciphered by many mobile phones. When a mobile phone that is equipped with a camera and QR code reading application scans the code, the device will open a Web browser

and display the DDI Alliance home page. The DDI Alliance QR code is provided as a high resolution JPEG file so that it can be easily integrated into any type of printed materials from brochures to posters.

New Paper on DDI and Relational Databases Published

The Alliance is pleased to announce the publication of a new paper in the Working Paper Series - "[Representing and Utilizing DDI in Relational Databases](#)," by Alerk Amin, Ingo Barkow, Stefan Kramer, David Schiller, and Jeremy Williams. The paper resulted from a workshop hosted by the [Leibniz Institute for Educational Research and Educational Information](#) (DIPF) in Frankfurt, Germany, on April 7-8, 2011.

Training Meeting Held

A small group met before the EDDI meeting in Gothenburg, Sweden, to establish [a set of principles](#) to serve as a foundation for DDI training. The principles are based on those developed by the Data Liberation Initiative in Canada but tailored to DDI training. Comments on the training principles are welcomed.

DDI Agency ID Registrar Needed

The [DDI registry of agency IDs](#) is now up and running, and

EDDI participants showed their creativity in these festive holiday cookies.

pending requests for agency IDs during 2011 have been fulfilled. The registered agencies should all be discoverable using the search on the registry site.

The Alliance needs a volunteer to assume the administrative duties of approving new requests for agency IDs. This work involves determining if requests are legitimate and are in line with the rules agreed to by the Expert Committee and then formally approving or rejecting the requests using an interface built for this purpose. The registrar should also record any issues discovered and bring them to the attention of the Alliance. If you are interested in this work, which involves a minimal time commitment, please contact the [DDI Director](#).